

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

2nd International Conference on Sustainable Fisheries (ICSF) 2022

"Fisheries for Achieving SDGs"

16-18 SEPTEMBER

Faculty of Fisheries
Sylhet Agricultural University
Sylhet-3100, Bangladesh
www.sau.ac.bd

ADOPTION OF IMPROVED SALT-SHRIMP (*Penaeus monodon*) INTEGRATED AQUACULTURE PRACTICES IN TRADITIONAL SALT PRODUCTION AREAS OF COX'S BAZAR

Seikh Razibul Islam^{1*}, Rezaul Hoque¹, Azharul Islam Shabuj¹, Md. Sariful Alam¹
& Muhammad Meezanur Rahman¹

¹WorldFish Bangladesh and South Asia Office, Dhaka-1212, Bangladesh

*Email: s.islam@cgiar.org

Development of appropriate technologies to integrate aquaculture in salt farms are required to reduce risk, diversify income, increase food security and nutrition uptake and generate employment for the salt farmers in Cox's Bazar district. The baseline of shrimp aquaculture production in the area is 100 kg per ha. The objective of the study was to assess the production performance of shrimp monoculture in six newly constructed aquaculture ponds (218.7±124.2 m²) in the salt farms at Cox's Bazar Sadar and Teknaf sub districts. Specific pathogen-free (SPF) shrimp (*Penaeus monodon*) were stocked @ 4 post larvae per square meter and reared for 90 days during March-May in 2021 and 2022. Water quality including water temperature (°C) and salinity (g/l) were recorded daily, dissolved oxygen (DO) (mg/l), transparency (cm), water level (cm), water pH, ammonia (mg/l), alkalinity (mg/l), phosphate (mg/l), nitrite (mg/l) and nitrate (mg/l) were recorded weekly, and growth and health status (visual observation the clinical signs of diseases) were recorded fortnightly. Shrimp were fed with a commercial diet of a national fish feed company. Analysis of physical and chemical attributes of water quality in the ponds showed significant differences in temperature (°C), salinity (g/l), dissolved oxygen (mg/l) and transparency (cm) between the ponds at Cox's Bazar Sadar and Teknaf but were within the recommended ranges of shrimp culture. In 2022, a higher survival rate and production were found in both locations compared to 2021 (Table 1). The better results in 2022 could be explained by improved routine management including timely feeding, water quality monitoring and health status monitoring. The improved technologies showed a 500% increase in shrimp production compared to baseline. Further improvement and dissemination of technologies can be achieved through training of the farmers and availability of the resources to improve management and biosecurity (quality post-larvae, feed and water quality monitoring).

Table 1. Mean weight, survival rates, production and feed conversion ratio (FCR) of two production cycles both in Cox's Bazar Sadar and Teknaf (n=6)

Production year	Number of ponds	Days of Culture (DoC)	Mean weight (g)	Survival rate (%)	Production (kg/ha)	FCR
2021	6	90	21.1±2.3	45.8±12.3	402±174	2.1±0.5
2022	6	90	18.6±2.0	79.4±10.4	590±112	1.3±0.1